

PSYCHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF DEVELOPING SELF- MANAGEMENT SKILLS IN STUDENT YOUTH CHARACTERISTICS

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Abstract

This article discusses the psychological characteristics of developing self-management skills in student youth, and provides detailed information about the importance of self-management in the educational process, knowledge acquisition, and finding one's place in society.

Keywords: Student youth, education, psychological characteristics, self-management, activity, skill

From the very first days of independence, the idea of forming and educating a fully developed individual was defined as a priority task for us. These tasks require a comprehensive approach to each person in our society, especially children and their upbringing. The comprehensive development of an individual depends to a certain extent on the educational process, its organization, and the methods and means of its implementation. The optimal foundation for successful education and knowledge acquisition is the harmonious formation of educational and intellectual skills and abilities in a person, along with indicators such as self-awareness, self-esteem, self-management, and cognition. Solving any problem begins with studying its theoretical foundations.

In the field of world psychology, various theories about personality development and growth have been created. Researchers take different positions in studying human personality and have unique approaches to illuminating the essence of the problem. Particularly, if we focus on a person's self-management, first of all, the phrase "self-" added to the term "self-management" reflects the subject's abilities to:

- be aware of their own free active actions and purposefully manage them;
- identify both the objective, rational-logical foundations of specific activity actions, as well as their personal-value basis;
- determine their interrelationships and adapt them to the context of the entire system of basic personal needs and values, spiritual goals and thoughts, as well as to the essence of self-awareness.

From a genetic perspective, self-control manifests as a unique human characteristic and a general function of the psyche, allowing individuals to emerge as creators, executors, and controllers of their activities, behaviors, and overall lifestyle. Self-regulation refers to a person's general ability to be the subject of their goal-directed activity, consistently realized in numerous individual actions of such activity. In other words, self-regulation exists both as a general ability of a person who is the subject of their activity and as a process of realizing this ability in specific individual actions of activity, behavior, communication, and so forth.

When O.A. Konopkin discussed the relationship between the concepts of "activity" and "self-regulation," he emphasized that they coexist and are implemented inseparably, complementing each other, and sometimes even impeding one another. However, they cannot substitute for each other because they emphasize incompatible aspects of human free activity. The concept of "activity" performs a semantic function related to the practical transformation of reality, with its methods corresponding to objective logic.

The concept of self-governance emphasizes that a person is the subject, creator, and owner of their own activity. The main aspect of result-oriented real activity is the executive action aimed at purposefully modifying the activity. Self-management is not only an internal psychological process directly related to carrying out the activity, but also a force that monitors the process of its implementation.

No changes occur from striving to "be better" than others, attempting to change, or from the demands, requests, and persuasions of loved ones. Self-regulation (from Latin *regulare* - to regulate, to adjust) is a systematically organized individual's conscious influence on their own psyche with the aim of changing its characteristics in the desired direction.

In every person's life and activities, the problem of regulating behavior in the changing conditions of the surrounding reality is of great importance. According to modern views, the meaningful characteristic of a person's entire psyche is precisely the ability to self-regulate goal-oriented activity and "create oneself," which makes a person a free and conscious subject in their life and activities. In the processes of self-management, the unity of relatively distinct stages, aspects, possibilities, functions, processes, abilities, and other elements is realized in the entire richness of the psyche. In general, the concept of "self-management" has an interdisciplinary nature. Self-regulation is a systemic process that ensures adequate adaptability to conditions and flexibility at all stages of life and activity.

In the works of many authors, there are attempts to isolate the psychological aspect of self-regulation. The emergence and development of ideas about self-

regulation occurred in close connection with such areas of psychological research as activity regulation, types of activity, motivation, will, freedom, self-determination, responsibility, and decision-making, as well as in the context of the problem of the general structure and dynamics of human activity.

The works of I.M. Sechenov and I.P. Pavlov laid the foundation for the formation of understanding the regulatory nature of mental phenomena and processes. V.M. Bekhterev, as well as his students and followers L.F. Lazursky, M.Ya. Basov, and V.N. Myasishev, made significant contributions to presenting and revealing the main aspects of mental self-regulation problems. According to V.M. Bekhterev, mental self-regulation is a person's conscious influence on their sphere of mental phenomena

(mental processes, states, characteristics) with the aim of maintaining or changing the nature of their functioning. Therefore, self-development (and participation in self-management as one of its most important forms) cannot be considered merely as something desirable. The social demand is becoming increasingly relevant: developing individual responsibility for its formation. Such an approach largely allows overcoming the idea of upbringing as merely an external influence.

The individual is at the center of their own development, encompassing the resources and mechanisms of personal dynamics. Self-governance of student youth aims to create favorable conditions for the continuous personal growth of each student and the formation of professionally important qualities in future specialists. Today, the priority areas of self-governing bodies include organizational activities within the student environment, protecting students' interests and rights, and fostering competitive specialists who should possess a range of competencies: organizational-managerial, communicative, and creative.

A student who is inclined towards organizational activities and has shown the most active participation in the education system, for example, has the opportunity to join the self-governance system. Performing the role of a student leader leads to self-education not only through self-affirmation and self-awareness but also by taking responsibility for one's decisions and actions. It strengthens the ability to be extroverted as an opportunity to withstand significant social activity, developing the ability to achieve goals not through commands and destructive criticism, but through persuasion, coordination, and explanation. While representing the interests of students before the school administration, student leaders must, as quickly as possible, objectively reflect the concerns of teachers, be able to convey them to

students, and predict the direction of further development of the school's educational system.

The presence of existing self-governing bodies in the educational institution has made it possible to almost completely remove the responsibility of organizing cultural events from the staff of the departments. This is not only about the quality of extracurricular activities

does not diminish, but, on the contrary, allows students to open up most easily and fully. On the other hand, self-governance contributes to the improvement of the student community, its transition to a higher stage of development, and the formation of pedagogically appropriate relationships among its members.

The implementation of information activities by student self-governance bodies ensures the organization and functioning of the information space in the school, covering the most important events in the life of the student community.

The main criterion for the effectiveness of student self-governance is increasing the level of activity of each student in various areas. Ongoing monitoring is carried out based on the analysis of measures in connection with the work being conducted in schools.

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